

Activity-Design Philosophies

Presentation of information is becoming more and more complex today which, in turn, requires one to use appropriate and refined tools for the audience to understand the data. PowerPoint presentation becomes the best option when presenting the information since it enables one to create a series of cues that are very easy to understand and to remember.

There are several best practices for preparing power points presentations or just simply to [buy research outlines](#). One of the practices is to minimize the number of slides to avoid confusing and overwhelming the audience. Another best practice to consider when preparing PowerPoint presentations is making them simple. An annoying, cluttered or complicated background can be a source of distraction for the audience. The slides should have plenty of 'negative space' or 'white space'. The less visual clutter appears on the slides, the more powerful the visual message is.

Choosing the right font type and size will be a key consideration, since the fonts transmit subtle information about themselves and the presenter. The font type and size should be consistent throughout the presentation. Moreover, it is important to pay attention to punctuation, grammar and capitalization throughout the presentation to make it professional.

Limited use of bullet points is another practice that can ensure the audience remains active. A single slide should contain only one bullet, which in turn comprises of one main point. In addition, graphics and animations should be of a high quality. Developing one's own graphics is critical and copying graphics from the Internet should be avoided.

When making the presentation, one of the best practices is to keep from reading the presentation word by word. This makes the audience bored. Moreover, holding one's end is very important to prevent the audience from zoning out and watching the slides like a television.

It is also important to make the presentation interactive by asking questions about an up-coming slide. Most importantly, one should hide the pointer as it can be a source of distraction to the audience. Considering all of the abovementioned, I choose PowerPoint as the best of the best mode of making future presentations.